

Organization of the dataset

This report is an auxiliary document to the dataset. If using the data please cite:

Hoult, R. D., Peel, M., Duffield, C., Lessons from flipping subjects in engineering: the effectiveness of student learning in a flipped environment at the University level. Submitted to *Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice.*

The paper describes the results of a research investigation undertaken in Hoult *et al.* (2020); in the research paper, the “flipped classroom” approach is employed for two engineering subjects undertaken at the University of Melbourne. The approach includes providing the delivery of lectures online, rather than using the traditional approach of providing lectures in person. Furthermore, the students were given compulsory quiz questionnaires after each part of an online lecture to reflect, review and have a change of activity. The students enrolled in the two subjects were still given formal class time (e.g. workshops), where they would undertake interactive and collaborative activities related to the online lecture material. Surveys were provided to the students at the beginning of the semester to understand their perceptions on different learning activities. It is shown that students who did well on the quiz questionnaires also did well in the subject, where evidence is provided to show a correlation between quiz questionnaire scores and final grades in both subjects. The survey results provide some evidence to suggest that the flipped classroom method could provide students a better learning experience for subjects at the University level, if implemented in a way that promotes active and student-centered learning. Some recommendations are provided based on the results of this research for the implementation of the flipped classroom method for future subjects at the University level.

This paper describes the data organization available on Zenodo associated with the research paper.

Organization of the data

All of the dataset can be downloaded from a publicly accessible platform Zenodo, at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2580024. The structure of the data folders is summarized in Figure 1. The data is organized in order of the results of the main paper and the separate programs that were used to derive the results.

Figure 1 Data organization for the paper

The data is separated into the two subjects that were the focus of this research investigation, ENEN20002 (“Earth Processes for Engineering”) and CVEN30010 (“Engineering Risk Analysis”).

The subfolders within the main subject folders are the same and are explained below.

1. “YouTube Analytics”

This folder contains all of the data extracted from YouTube Analytics for the online lecture videos. This data was primarily used to derive the lecture attendance (i.e., Equation 1 in the corresponding paper). The files downloaded from YouTube Analytics are .csv files and are organized in subfolders corresponding to the different week of lectures; a typically semester has twelve weeks of teaching content.

The two Microsoft Excel files in this folder (“dates.xlsx” and “videos.xlsx”) contain the dates corresponding to each week of lecture content and the different video titles with corresponding duration (i.e., time in minutes, seconds) and number of total views.

The MATLAB file in this folder (“read_files.m”) is a program written to extract the data in order to calculate the lecture attendance. This file outputs images that correspond to the following figures in the research paper: Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6, and Figure 7.

2. “Quiz”

This folder contains the extracted quiz questionnaire results from the Learning Management System; the Microsoft Excel file (“quiz_results.xlsx”) contains the extracted information.

The MATLAB file (“quiz_results.m”) is a program that inputs the quiz results and outputs images corresponding to the following figures in the research paper: Figure 8 and Figure 10.

It should be noted that Figure 9 and Figure 11 of the corresponding research paper show the correlations between the overall quiz scores and the final grades in the respective subject. Unfortunately, the data to produce these figures are not included in this dataset, as this would require personal student information, such as name and student numbers, to be published.

3. “Final Grades”

This folder contains the final grade distributions of the students enrolled in the respective subjects. It should be noted that any information regarding individual student names or numbers have not been published here. The two Microsoft Excel files (“bin_grades.xlsx” and “normal_distributions.xlsx”) contain all of the extracted information regarding the final grade distributions.

The MATLAB file in this folder (“histogram_final_grades.m”) is a program that inputs the grade distributions and outputs images that correspond to the following figures in the research paper: Figure 12.